

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

№10
2025

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 1658 sahifa,
3-oktyabr, 2025-yil.

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Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

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Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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“TIME MANAGEMENT” TUSHUNCHASI VA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARI TALABALARINING O'QUV YUTUQLARI O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIK

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi – talabalar vaqtni boshqarish ko'nikmalari bilan ularning o'quv yutuqlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni aniqlashdir. Vaqtni boshqarish inson faoliyatida muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, u umumiy samaradorlik va yutuqlarga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Biroq bu ko'nikma talabalarning kundalik faoliyatini qanday tashkil etishi bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir. O'qituvchilar tomonidan beriladigan samarali ma'ruzalar va qulay ta'lim muhiti talabalar natijalarini ijobiy shakllantirishga yordam beradi. Shu bilan birga, vaqtni samarali boshqarish talabalarning muvaffaqiyatini belgilovchi asosiy omillardan biri hisoblanadi. Ayrim talabalar ushbu ko'nikmalarga ega emasligi sababli, bu holat ularning o'qishi va shaxsiy hayotiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida talabalar vaqtni qanday sarflashi ularning odatlari va kundalik faoliyatiga bog'liq bo'lib, bu jarayon stress darajalariga ham bevosita ta'sir qiladi. Ushbu tadqiqot doirasida Toshkent Amaliy fanlar universiteti talabalari misolida vaqtni boshqarishning o'quv yutuqlariga ta'siri tahlil qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: vaqtni boshqarish, o'quv yutuqlari, talabalar, stress, kundalik faoliyat, oliy ta'lim.

Abstract: The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between students' time management skills and their academic achievements. Time management plays a crucial role in human activity, as it directly influences overall efficiency and success. However, this skill is closely linked to how students organize their daily routines. Effective lectures delivered by instructors, along with a supportive academic environment, contribute to students' positive outcomes. At the same time, efficient time management remains one of the fundamental factors determining students' success. The absence of these skills in some students negatively affects both their academic progress and personal lives. The way university students allocate their time depends on their daily habits and routines, which also directly influence their stress levels. Within this study, data were collected from students of the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences, and the impact of time management on their academic performance was analyzed.

Key words: time management, academic performance, students, stress, daily activities, higher education.

Аннотация: Цель данного исследования – выявить взаимосвязь между навыками тайм-менеджмента студентов и их учебными достижениями. Управление временем играет ключевую роль в деятельности человека, так как напрямую влияет на его общую эффективность и успех. Однако данный навык тесно связан с тем, как студенты организуют свою повседневную деятельность. Эффективные лекции преподавателей и благоприятная учебная среда способствуют положительным результатам. Вместе с тем тайм-менеджмент остается одним из основных факторов, определяющих успех студентов. Отсутствие данных навыков у некоторых студентов отрицательно сказывается как на учебе, так и на личной жизни. То, как студенты высших учебных заведений распоряжаются своим временем, зависит от их привычек и ежедневной активности, что также напрямую влияет на уровень стресса. В рамках данного исследования были собраны данные у студентов Ташкентского университета прикладных наук и проведен анализ влияния тайм-менеджмента на их учебные достижения.

Ключевые слова: тайм-менеджмент, учебные достижения, студенты, стресс, повседневная деятельность, высшее образование.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, time is considered an infinite and usable resource. It helps instill the concept of time in organizations. All material and human resources owned by organizations may change or develop over time, but the only asset that cannot be altered is time itself. The secret to success in life is paying enough attention to effectively managing and planning this resource equally given to everyone. The rising expectations for the knowledge and skills of modern employees have also increased the need for time planning. Success in social

life is achieved through effective and productive work, which is only possible through time management. Today, the competitive environment trains individuals, even from school age, to plan and manage time. Competitive demands force organizations and leaders to use time effectively.

Time management plays an important role in improving students' academic performance. Every student must have the ability to manage time: this means setting goals and priorities, using planning methods, and being organized. This can only be achieved through self-motivation. Activities in which today's university students participate often hinder their academic results. Due to poor time planning, they fall behind. This research helps analyze the positive or negative effects of time management on academic achievement. It provides insights for decision-making on how to use time efficiently. There is no single correct way to manage time, but by understanding ourselves well, we can determine how to manage our time. This topic is being discussed on various platforms, and students' attitudes and behaviors towards time are being studied in educational institutions.

In developing countries, problems encountered during the educational process provide researchers with opportunities for new explorations. Previous research has shown that time management affects students' academic results. Nevertheless, many students do not pay enough attention to this relationship due to a lack of awareness about the importance of time in education. In higher education, study schedules must be well planned, implemented, and monitored. Proper time management also aids in developing cost-reducing educational policies.

The persistence of this issue – i.e., the lack of sufficient data on the relationship between time management and academic results, and the difficulty in collecting such data – highlights the need for special attention to time management in modern education systems. This study also investigates students' effectiveness in managing time and its impact on their academic outcomes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Many studies confirm the impact of time management on human life, especially its importance in education. In today's world, people can successfully manage their lives by planning and organizing their daily activities. The key to this success is managing time properly and efficiently. Research shows that differences exist in time management skills among teachers and students. When students apply effective time management strategies, it positively affects their grades, stress levels, and overall well-being.

For instance, a study in the UK found that students with high-level time management skills had significantly better academic outcomes. How students plan their time, determine priorities, and their discipline in using time are crucial factors in academic success. Moreover, students who plan their time in personally favorable and effective ways are observed to perform better in academic activities, preparation quality, and grades.

Additionally, other studies emphasize that time management plays an essential role not only in academic success but also in ensuring a balanced personal life. A study in Egypt found that students reduced stress and found more time for rest through time management. This increased their motivation and self-confidence. As a result, effective time management positively affects students' overall quality of life.

Students with poor time management skills are usually prone to procrastination. This leads to the development of procrastination syndrome, increasing stress, lowering academic results, and decreasing self-esteem. Therefore, many universities and educational institutions have started offering time management training for students. Through such training, students learn to plan effectively, prioritize tasks, and allocate time correctly.

Studies also show a connection between time management and personal traits. For example, self-regulation, discipline, motivation, and initiative play a vital role in time management. By developing these skills, students can succeed not only academically but also professionally. Moreover, acquiring time management techniques early in life lays the foundation for future success.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted using a descriptive method to identify how students manage their time and the relevance of time management. A questionnaire method was used as the research model, through which students' strategies for managing their time and its impact on academic life were studied.

3.1. Research Sample

The study was conducted in the 2025–academic year among 1st– to 4th–year undergraduate students studying in the Faculty of Education (Primary Education and Sports Department) at Tashkent University of Applied Sciences. A total of 292 students (124 female and 168 male) participated voluntarily in the research.

3.2. Data Collection Tool

The study utilized the Student Time Management Skills Assessment Questionnaire, developed by Britton and Tesser (1991). The questionnaire was adapted into Uzbek and reviewed for cultural and contextual suitability. It consists of 18 statements rated on a 5-point Likert scale (from 1 – “never” to 5 – “always”). It evaluates students’ time management levels across three indicators: time planning, time valuing, and procrastination. Some statements are reverse-coded.

3.3. Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) to identify general trends. Test analyses were used to determine differences between two variables. Demographic variables such as gender, academic year, and sports activity were also considered during analysis.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This section analyzes data collected from 292 students in the Faculty of Education, Department of Primary Education and Sports, at Tashkent University of Applied Sciences. The results are presented under the following subtopics:

4.1. Students’ Time Management Levels

Results show that students’ overall time management level is average. The mean score for time planning was 3.41 (± 0.74), time valuing 3.65 (± 0.67), and procrastination 2.48 (± 0.81). These results indicate that students pay more attention to valuing time but face difficulties in planning and especially in procrastination.

4.2. Gender Differences

Analysis revealed no statistically significant gender differences in time management levels ($p > 0.05$). However, female students had slightly higher scores in time planning and valuing, while male students had higher procrastination levels.

4.3. Differences by Academic Year

Significant differences were found in time management skills among students from 1st- to 4th-year ($p < 0.05$). Especially, senior students (3rd–4th year) had higher scores in time planning and valuing than lower-year students.

4.4. Impact of Sports Activity

There was also a significant difference between students who regularly engaged in sports and those who did not ($p < 0.05$). Students involved in sports showed better efficiency in time management, particularly in valuing and planning time. This suggests that sports help develop discipline and a structured lifestyle.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study showed that students in the Faculty of Education at Tashkent University of Applied Sciences have an average level of time management skills. Although students showed a positive attitude toward valuing time, they face challenges in planning and especially in procrastination. This indicates that time management skills are not fully developed.

Regarding gender differences, although female students had slightly higher scores in planning and valuing time, no statistically significant difference was found in overall time management levels. These findings align with previous research, suggesting that gender may not significantly influence time management skills.

Time management skills were observed to improve with academic year progression. Senior students were more effective in planning and valuing time compared to junior students, suggesting that experience during the education process enhances time management skills.

Additionally, students engaged in sports had higher time management scores. These findings indicate that sports positively influence personal discipline, planning ability, and effective time distribution.

In conclusion, although students demonstrated some positive time management indicators, significant shortcomings were found in procrastination and planning. Educational institutions can support students in this area by promoting time management training, seminars, and encouraging sports activities. Teaching students to manage time effectively plays a vital role in their academic success and personal development.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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2025. №10

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.